

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND EARTH OBSERVATION FOR EFFICIENT RAW MATERIALS MAPPING

by

Krištof Oštir¹, Rushaniia Gubaidullina², Irene Zananiri³, Marko Savolainen⁴, Mihaela Violeta Gheorghes⁵, Marta Alonso Fernández⁶, and Ana Cláudia Teodoro⁷

¹*University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering, Jamova cesta 2, Ljubljana, Slovenia*

E-mail: kristof.ostir@fgg.uni-lj.si

²*Montanuniversität Leoben, Chair of Mining Engineering and Mineral Economics, Franz Josef-Straße 18, Leoben, Austria*

³*Hellenic Survey of Geology & Mineral Exploration Institution, 1 Spirou Loui str., Olympic Village, Acharnae, Greece*

⁴*VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd., Mikrokatu 1, Kuopio, Finland*

⁵*GMV Innovating Solutions S.R.L., Calea Floreasca 246C, Skytower, 32nd floor, Bucharest, Romania*

⁶*International Center for Advanced Materials and raw materials of Castile and Leon, León Technology Park, Main Building, C/ Julia Morros s/n Primera Planta, Of. 106, 24009, Armunia, León, Spain*

⁷*Department of Geosciences, Environment and Spatial Planning, and Institute of Earth Sciences (ICT), University of Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre 687, Porto, Portugal*

The Secure and Sustainable Supply of Raw Materials for EU Industry – S34I project aims to increase European autonomy over raw materials resources through research and development of new data-driven methods for the analysis of Earth observation (EO) data. The aim is to improve the systematic exploration of minerals and ensure continuous monitoring of all activities, i.e., extraction, closure, and post-closure. The project involves 19 partners from 12 European countries. The partners have balanced expertise and come from large industries, SMEs, private non-profit and public research organisations, public institutions, and academia.

The project uses various techniques and methods, including satellite data, airborne systems, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), underwater hyperspectral imaging (UHI), ground-based measurements, and traditional in-situ methods. We are using a cloud-based geospatial processing infrastructure based on CloudFerro Copernicus DIAS, which will enable the development of advanced methods and models derived from EO data. Using artificial intelligence, we are supporting the technical experiments and pilot validations/demonstrations for the six pilot use cases in:

- *Onshore exploration* (Áramo, Spain), where the epithermal (epigenetic) mineralisation of Cobalt-Copper-Nickel is hosted within certain stratigraphic limestone units within the Upper Namurian of the Carboniferous Period.
- *Shallow water exploration* (Ria de Vigo, Spain), where the geological conditions onshore and offshore shallow waters are suitable for placers finding (primary mineral source, weathering environment, means of transportation).
- *Extraction* (Gummern, Austria), a quarry that produces roughly 1 million tons of high-quality marble, both in open-pit and underground extraction sites. 400000 tons of material must be transported to local waste dumps, as this material does not fulfil the quality criteria of the major customers in the pharma, paper, and automotive industries.
- *Closure/post-closure* (Lausitz, Germany, Aijala and Keretti-Outokumpu, Finland). The Aijala mine and processing plant in Southwest Finland closed in 1961. The tailings are 2 million tons,

of which a small part is placed as mine backfill with the side stone. The Lausitz mining and post-mining landscapes cover approx. 7000 km², including many refilled small- to large-scale former pits, remaining lakes, open active and inactive pits and channels used to release pumped water to surface water bodies.

Figure 1: S34I pilot site locations and their characteristics, including deposit types and land cover/land use.

Mining sites were selected from key EU mining regions, with criteria covering all phases of life-cycle mining and different sizes and Critical Raw Materials. S34I aims to take a holistic view to cover all challenges identified in the theme and has searched for accessible and representative sites for the use cases.

The cloud infrastructure put in place enables the analysis of geospatial data from a whole range of EO sensors (radar, multispectral, hyperspectral, and thermal), the integration and processing of data from different sources (satellite, UAV, UHI, in-situ) and the analysis of datasets for the challenges prioritised at each mining pilot site. We are developing prototype implementations for promising algorithms for data integration and processing, spatial analysis, spatial monitoring, modelling, and mapping. The focus is on technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), geospatial artificial intelligence (GeoAI), Big Data processing, knowledge representation, modelling and mathematical optimisation.

In particular, the innovative, promising methods for the prototype are used:

- *At the onshore exploration site*, where improved maps and techniques to map potential Co target areas using support vector machine (SVM), random forest (RF) and artificial neural networks (ANN) to create an ensemble AI method and exploit different satellite-based datasets (Landsat-9, Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, PRISMA and WorldView-3) are developed. Co-predictive

mapping improves by using self-organizing map (SOM) for pre-processing exploration datasets and combining geological and remote sensing based models to detect the hydrothermal alterations associated with Co.

- *At shallow waters exploration site*, where AI/ML post-processing of UHI to build a spectral library for ground-truthing and correlation with onshore Earth observation data (PRISMA, Worldview, Sentinel, Landsat-8/9) that allows proposing a new methodology for ground truthing and detection of mineral deposits in coastal areas. Shallow waters and shoreline sediment distribution are geologically studied regarding the placers' deposit occurrences to delineate the prospective areas.
- *At the extraction site*, improved volume maps of mining waste deposits using Structure from Motion (SfM) photogrammetry using a multispectral camera mounted on a UAV with an operational range compatible with Sentinel-2 are being used. Ground instability maps are obtained through new InSAR methods for the combination of multiple-satellite SAR data (e.g., Sentinel-1 and COSMO-SkyMED) collected at different bands to compute long-term 2D (up-down, east-west) ground displacement time-series on a high-resolution (HR) grid. Mineral stockpile volume estimation through satellite photogrammetry and 3D-stereo images from optical and SAR data is being computed.
- *At closure/post-closure site*, where ground instability maps by SBAS-InSAR are analysed on Sentinel-1 enhanced super-resolution datasets obtained through DL models trained on VHR space-based datasets from Copernicus Contributing Missions (i.e., TerraSAR-X, CosmoSkyMed, ICEYE). Acid mine drainage (AMD) maps by AI predictivity of Fe (and other AMD constituents) and quantitative pH mapping using RF, ANN, and SOM and exploiting Sentinel-2 and other HR Earth observation datasets are estimated.

In S34I, we are developing a multi-scale and multi-platform analysis methodology to coherently exploit EO data from different spatial and spectral scales obtained from different remote sensing platforms, mainly satellites, airborne and UAVs. This methodology will be a basis for building processing pipelines for local, regional, national, and European geoscience services.

Space-based remote sensing and geospatial information harmonisation developed by the project team ensures that state-of-the-art modelling and geological mapping comply with EU data quality principles and EDGI mechanisms for harmonisation and standardisation of interoperability. We pay particular attention to improving geological integration at the land-sea interface and ensuring that research datasets become open, unbiased geoscience data for future use by researchers, policymakers and society at large.

In addition to space-based data collection, special attention is also given to non-space-based methods. We focus on in-situ data collection both on land and in shallow waters, either to create the required spectral libraries that can be used as ground truth/calibration of EO methods or to generate quality datasets for training AI models and make them available as open, high-quality datasets. A ground truth spectral library on the seabed in shallow waters using UHI survey data and a ground truth spectral library on land exploration sites using visible and near-infrared (VNIR) – shortwave infrared (SWIR) survey data are currently being created. We are acquiring airborne very high-resolution (VHR) Light Detection and Ranging (lidar) and hyperspectral datasets and applying data fusion techniques. These data are processed using the algorithms of ML to automate the pre-processing of aerial hyperspectral data. In doing so, only a minimal amount of ground truth data is required to avoid lengthy and expensive field survey campaigns, and only a minimum of expertise and tuning is required for mineral

identification. Hyperspectral data processing, mineralogical characterisation, site mining waste deposits extraction, and in-situ geochemical sampling in water and solid soil complement EO data collection.

Figure 2: CloudFerro Copernicus DIAS geospatial processing infrastructure.

Prototype processing pipelines for promising algorithms for data integration and processing, spatial analysis, spatial monitoring, modelling, and mapping are being developed. The pipelines of methods and prototyping EO-based added value services for mining stakeholders are being prepared for three services categories:

- *Raw materials deposits mapping*, using the EO-based services related to gaining geospatial intelligence on new or more accurate existing Critical Raw Material deposits. This applies to both land and shallow water exploration sites.
- *Early warnings*, to develop the EO-based services related to early warnings to reduce workers and surrounding population risks (including instability and volumes). This applies to both extraction and closure sites.
- *Environmental monitoring*, to apply EO-based services related to environmental monitoring on health and ecosystems. This applies to both extraction and closure sites.

We are running benchmarking and synergies among various methods for similar purposes to support decisions in different phases of the mining life cycle at different scales.

The value of the results will be demonstrated to stakeholders, i.e., geological surveys, the mining industry, local communities, and policymakers. The project will support future systematic mineral exploration and continuous monitoring of extraction, closure, and post-closure activities to promote the secure and sustainable supply of raw materials to Europe while enhancing its resilience and independence from non-EU sources.

